

An Automatic Monitoring System for Vehicle Drivers

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Abstract— it is a key important issue to prevent life and property from the accidents caused by vehicles of drivers. Alcohol can, speed, drowsy driving, and sudden heart attack are the major causes for road accidents, which can lead to severe physical injuries, deaths and significant economic losses. Various methods have been proposed to detect automatically those causes to prevent accidents. We have addressed an automatic system to provide protection of drivers and travelers by dint of computer vision techniques along with embedded systems and mobile communication methodologies. Sleepy modes detection and then awaken of driver have been controlled with computer vision methods, while mobile communication and car control have been performed by embedded system components. Primary implemented method showed its potential effectiveness. If our system could be adopted in the future, the accidents related to drivers would be reduced significantly in all over the world.

Keywords— Drowsiness Detection for Vehicle Drivers, Automatic Monitoring System, Eye Tracking, Embedded Systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

THE health and safety of people on the roads and highways must be taken into measures with high accountability.

Cruising drivers may fall asleep or start in feeling the symptoms of a coronary thrombosis (i.e., a possible heart attack). Such situations can lead to irrevocable aftermath. Heavy vehicles (e.g., bus, strongly built cart or wagon for transporting heavy loads) would cause more danger on flow traffic than those of light vehicles. Alcohol and speed are legitimately directed toward the major causes of road accidents, yet another deadly factor is falling asleep at the wheel (usually known as tired driving, drowsy driving, or fatigued driving). Drowsy driving is a major cause of motor vehicle accidents, and it can impair the human brain as much as alcohols can [1]. According to a 1998 survey, 23% of adults have fallen asleep while driving [2]. According to the United States Department of Transportation, male drivers admit to have fallen asleep while driving twice as much as female drivers [3]. In the United States, 250000 drivers fall asleep at the wheel every day, according to the Division of Sleep Medicine at Harvard Medical School and in a national poll by the National Sleep Foundation, 54% of adult drivers said they had driven while drowsy during the past year with 28% saying they had actually fallen asleep while driving. According to the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, drowsy driving is a factor in more than 100000 crashes, resulting in 1550 deaths and 40000 injuries annually in the USA [4]. A sudden heart attack, in a minor occasion, of a driver of heavy vehicle would cause irreversible consequences as well. However, it is important to prevent life and property from the accidents caused by either alcohol can or speed or drowsy driving or heart attack.

As technology is emerging part and presell of human lives

in this century, especially transportation networks are enormously getting be improved. Automobile software technologies are also developing near with transportation networks day by day.

Many efforts have been underway for vehicle safety system. For instances, in an effort to make driving safer for both the occupants of the vehicle and their fellow road users, Mercedes-Benz have been working on a system since 2007 that recognizes tiredness related changes in personal driving style and warns the driver when it is time to take a break [5]. Toyota introduced a vehicle safety system called driver monitoring system [6], [7] in 2006 for Lexus models. The system used infrared sensors to monitor driver attentiveness. Specifically, the driver monitoring system included a CCD camera placed on the steering column which was capable of eye tracking, via infrared LED detectors. If the driver was not paying attention to the road ahead and a dangerous situation was detected, the system should warn the driver by flashing lights, warning sounds.

If no action was taken, the vehicle should apply the brakes (a warning alarm should sound followed by a brief automatic application of the braking system). In 2008, the Toyota Crown system went further and can detect if the driver would become sleepy by monitoring the eyelids. Detection of drowsy drivers of heavy vehicles can form the basis of a system to potentially reduce accidents related to drowsy driving. The aim of our effort is to minimize the involuntary loss of life and property caused by the drivers of heavy vehicles. We have proposed an automatic system to provide protection of drivers and travelers by dint of computer vision techniques along with embedded systems and mobile communication method-

ologies. Sleepy modes detection and then awaken of driver have been controlled with computer vision methods, while mobile communication and car control have been performed by embedded system components. Fig.1 depicts our proposed approach.

Fig. 1. Flow-Chart of the Proposed Model

If our system could be adopted in the future, the accidents related to drivers would be reduced significantly all over the world. The remaining part of this paper has been organized as follows: Section 2 some related cutting edge techniques. Section 3 delineates the proposed framework; Section 4 reports some experimental results; finally, Section 5 presents the conclusion of the work with little inkling for further investigation.

2 STATE-OF-THE-ART METHODS

Grace et al. [8] reported on efforts performed at the Carnegie Mellon Driving Research Center to develop such in vehicle driver monitoring systems. Commercial motor vehicle truck drivers were studied in actual fleet operations. The drivers operated vehicles that were equipped to measure vehicle performance and driver psychophysiological data. Based on this work, two drowsiness detection methods are being considered. The first is a video-based system that measures Percent Eyelid Closure (PERCLOS, which is defined as the proportion of time that a subject's eyes are closed over a specified period) a scientifically supported measure of drowsiness associated with slow eye closure. The second detection method is based on a model to estimate PERCLOS based on vehicle performance data. A non-parametric (neural network) model was used to estimate PERCLOS using measures associated with lane keeping, steering wheel movements and lateral accelera-

tion of the vehicle [8]. Drowsiness, stress, and lack of concentration caused by a variety of different factors is a serious problem in traffic. Many traffic accidents are due to these risky behaviors of the drivers. A system which recognizes the state of the driver and e.g. suggests breaks when stress level is too high or driver is too tired would enable large savings and reduces accident. Today different physiological sensor signals such as Electrocardiogram (ECG), Elektrookulogram (EOG), Electroencephalogram (EEG) and Pulse Oximeter (Oxygen saturation measurements) enable clinician to determine psychological and behavioral state with high accuracy. There are researchers working on developing intelligent systems help to monitor potential risky behaviors of drivers using sensor signals. Begum [9] discussed an overview and analysis of driver monitoring/alerting systems developments and implementations which are based on physiological sensor signals. Feng et al. [10] presented a data fusion method for the on-board detection of driver drowsiness in real time. Multiple sensors including camera to capture the driver's eye status, angle sensor to measure the driver's steering behavior, and clock to indicate the time on task were implemented. A data fusion framework based on Dempster-Shafer theory is built for modeling and combining the pieces of evidence, and to generate an overall inference of the driver's drowsiness level. The method has been validated in an experiment on a driving simulator. The results suggest that the data fusion process could reduce the uncertainty in the drowsiness inference and obtain a better system performance compared with any single sensor [10]. Kim et al. [11] proposed method of drowsiness detection with eyes open using Epworth Sleepiness Scale based power spectrum analysis. The fatigue state of the driver is one of the important factors that cause traffic accidents. Vision based facial expression recognition technique is the most prospective method to detect driver fatigue. Therefore, a system that can detect oncoming driver drowsiness and issue timely warning could help in preventing many accidents and consequently save money and reduce personal suffering. By mounting a small camera inside the car the face of driver can be monitored. Firstly the face is detected by using skin color algorithm and then eyes are detected by using Circular Hough transform. This paper describes a method to track the eyes and detect whether the eyes are closed or open. If the eyes are found closed for 8 consecutive frames, the system draws the conclusion that the driver is falling asleep and issues a warning signal. In the method of Devi et al. [12] a non-intrusive technique is used in which no sensors are used on vehicle part as well as on body of the driver which was used in intrusive technique cause irritation in long time driving. The designed system is working properly in diverse conditions such as changes in light, shadow, and slightly dark background. Vehicle safety traffic is a hot issue today. Because the factors of pre-warning decision are very complex, including weather, time, vehicle type, self-speed, relative speed and so on, those factors usually induces pre-warning decision of vehicle safety traffic not to meet real-time capability and high accuracy. Different weather, different vehicle types and different speeds require different pre-warning decisions. For the existing condition of the high ways in China, a vehicle safety traffic pre-warning

decision is proposed combining multi-sensor information fusion with fuzzy expert system. The factors of pre-warning decision are real-timely detected by multi-sensor information fusion and the decision is designed on fuzzy expert system. At last, the pre-warning decision is applied on high ways. The results show that the pre-warning decision reduces the rate of misreport and the rate of missing report of the pre-warning system and enhances stability and practicability. It sufficiently considers the existing condition of the high ways in China and the habits of drivers, so it is of wide application value [13]. Driver safety continues to be improved by advances in active safety technologies. In various advanced countries, regulations and New Car Assessment Program soon will require Autonomous Emergency Braking (AEB) and Lane Departure Warning (LDW). The market of recognition systems for active safety is continually expanding, in which a key element is image recognition technology for advanced safety vehicles. We have been developing core image recognition technologies for autonomous vehicles. These core technologies can be divided into 3 categories which are front, rear-view, and SurroundEye camera systems. First, we describe the SurroundEye view monitoring system using 4 cameras for parking assistance. Second, we describe the rear-view camera sensing system which is used for both rear-view monitoring and active safety technologies. Finally, we introduce active safety technologies using a front stereo camera. These systems require real-time processing, and robust sensing on outdoor environments [14]. A real-time rollover threat warning system (RWS) of heavy duty vehicle has been proposed [15]. The function of RWS is used to determine the rollover threat of heavy duty vehicle and warn the driver to adjust the operation during dangerous conditions. The paper suggests a new algorithm of rollover warning for heavy duty vehicle based on accurate PTR metric. The effectiveness of the RWS is validated by test data of heavy duty. The vehicle test results show that the RWS system is very suitable for application in rollover risk assessment and warning [15]. The rollover warning technology reported in this paper focuses on detection of heavy duty truck real-time rollover propensities. The paper suggests a new algorithm of rollover warning for heavy duty vehicle based on Kalman filter technology. Its feasibility for implementation in a heavy duty truck rollover threat detection system is demonstrated through vehicle dynamic simulation studies. The effectiveness of the rollover warning is validated by test data of heavy duty. It has been demonstrated that the proposed rollover warning system is very suitable for application in rollover risk assessment and warning [16].

3 IMPLEMENTATION STEPS

3.1 Pupil and Iris Detection

Eye detection and tracking as a tool is now more accessible than ever, and is growing in popularity amongst researchers of various disciplines. Eye tracking is the process of measuring either the point of gaze (where one is looking) or the motion of an eye relative to the head. An eye tracker is a device for measuring eye positions and eye movement. Nowadays, there exist many promising face detection algorithms. A lot of algo-

rithms for eye contour detection require the detection of eye positions to initialize eye templates. Thus eye position detection is important not only for face recognition and facial expression analysis but also for eye contour detection. Image-based eye detection approaches locate the eyes by exploiting eyes differences in appearance and shape from the rest of the face. To recognize sleeping mode of a driver, it is important to detect pupil and iris.

3.2 Drowsiness Detection

In this study, eye socket detection is achieved by using Haar Adaboost Classifier which uses pre trained cascade file already exists in OpenCV library [17]. Both two eye sockets are employed as the candidate regions to minimize the computational cost and probable misdetection for eye pupil detection. Eye sockets are shown with two separate rectangles and their mass centers in terms of intensity are marked as well. Depending on the Euclidean distance between the mass center and each pixel in each socket, the pixel with the minimum physical distance and highest darkness is considered as the probable pupil center. In order to find the eyeball boundary, pixels are scanned from outer to inner towards the candidate pupil center in 8 directions. Local minima and maxima regions in which pixels create high deviations in terms of intensity are marked and their Euclidean distances with the probable pupil center are averaged. By this method, elliptical model of eyeball is approximated with its centroid and two diameters. Finally, the greatness of the ratio x/y between the horizontal diameter x and vertical diameter y determines the drowsiness state.

3.3 Pulse Finding Case

A sphygmograph (pulse height analyzer which indicates graphically the movements or character of the pulse) is located to steering of vehicle. The pulse of the driver can be recorded through sphygmograph. The average of the pulse is calculated in every 10 minutes. A scope is specified by adding -20 and +20, in every time when the average is calculated. And then it is controlled that whether the current pulse is in the scope or not. If current pulse is not in the scope, the driver will see a warning at the indicator panel which is *Have a coffee break!* If no pulse, the vehicle stops and a message is sent to 112 about the driver pulse.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

4.1 Experimental Setup

Our proposed system contains image processing methodologies, embedded system, and mobile communication. For that reason it needs hardware, software, and image processing strategies. This three module works with coordinately for distinct status. Image processing technology was used for detecting drivers' sleepy mode or not. If the drivers' eyes close more than five seconds motors are stopped and alert the driver. This case has been programmed at *Processing* [18] environment that is Java based IDE. Embedded System strategy was used for prototype cars movement and detecting drivers pulse. The prototype car commands and *Processing* [18] communication controls with wireless technology. The pulse sen-

sor was used for checking drivers pulse and sends an SMS to health organizations. This case focuses on checking drivers' health and providing secure of passengers. This embedded system approach has been programmed at Arduino environment that is Java based IDE.

4.2 Dataset

We did not use any benchmark dataset to conduct experiments. However, we have used our own dataset.

4.3 Findings

We have implemented our proposed system using a small scale setup. Fig. 2 demonstrates some detection of our proposed system.

Fig. 2. Sample Snapshots from Proposed System

Outcome of our proposed system demonstrates the potential use of it in the application of heavy vehicles. The system can detect the drowsy driving and alarm the driver. It is able to send a sms to 112 service if case of the driver would not be awoken. The vehicle can be stopped if the sleeping driver would not be got up from sleep.

4.4 Shortcomings

The proposed system was tested with a small scale laboratory implementation. It is important to test the system with a large scale industrial implementation. Large scale simulation results would be also helpful.

5 CONCLUSION

We hinted an automatic system to provide protection of drivers and travelers using computer vision techniques, embedded systems, and mobile communication methodologies. Our system is mainly designed for heavy vehicles. Because vehicle drivers generally travel far places and they also drive their lorries at night. Then they can be sleepless and thus drowsy driving would be a consequence. Sleepy modes detection and then awoken of driver are controlled with computer vision methods, while mobile communication and car control are performed by embedded system components. Primary small scale implementation showed its potential effectiveness. If our system could be adopted in the future, the accidents related to drivers would reduce significantly in all over the world.

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